

RADx-UP Evidence Academy

Slide Template (edit for relevance to your project)

What is an Evidence Academy?

- An Evidence Academy is an engaged conference approach to understand the state-of-the-science, or the current evidence of COVID-19 testing and related factors in the populations most impacted.
- The COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy series is hosted by RADx-UP, bringing together researchers, community and governmental leaders to share their experiences, ideas, and recommendations to overcome disparities in COVID-19 testing.
- How the Evidence Academy relates to our work with RADx-UP (*tailor any specific information gained from the EA that applies to your project and/or community*)

COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy Themes

- The second Evidence Academy, **Looking Forward: Bridging Infrastructures for Equitable COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination**, centered around identifying promising practices that promote sustainable infrastructures for COVID-19 testing, vaccination, data sharing, and emergency preparedness now and in the future.
- The conference focused on six core themes:
 - **Policies to Support Routine & Surge COVID-19 Testing**
 - **Pandemic Preparedness**
 - **COVID-19 Testing in Schools**
 - **Strengthening Multi-Sector Partnerships**
 - **Data Sharing Equity**
 - **Establishing Communication Frameworks**

COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy Themes

COVID-19 TESTING (& VACCINE)

POLICIES, BIG AND SMALL

How can we help develop organizational, local, state, Tribal, and federal policies to promote wide-scale testing and vaccination? The latest research finds that:

- COVID-19 testing remains an important tool to reduce the spread of COVID-19 in communities.
- The policies that direct testing, screening, and vaccination strategies are as important as the technologies.
- To make testing, vaccinations, and contact tracing equitable, community members need multiple ways to get a COVID-19 test and vaccinations—such as at school, at work, at a drive/walk-thru testing site, or through a local mobile clinic.
- Organizations and local, and state, and Tribal governments will need to continually adapt policies to changing science.

COVID-19 SURGE & ROUTINE TESTING

How can communities conduct testing routinely to reduce the spread of COVID-19? The latest research finds that:

PANDEMIC PREPAREDNESS

How can we identify strategies to prevent negative health outcomes from COVID-19 or other public health emergencies? The latest research finds that:

- Federal, Tribal, state, and local governments should have coordinated response strategies to provide COVID-19 guidance to local health leaders, Tribal nations, and public health organizations and officials.
- In the Spring of 2020, a rapid shift to telemedicine helped slow the spread of COVID-19 among healthcare workers and patients. However, telehealth can present challenges to people without access to internet. Health systems and state, Tribal, and local governments should consider how to improve telehealth access for those who need it most.
- Health systems can surge the health workforce by maximizing community health workers; calling upon retired or inactive health workers; giving health professionals the skills they need to take on needed roles; and fast-tracking medical students.
- A national disease surveillance program could help monitor communities for outbreaks or hotspots and help inform policies around social distancing and travel restrictions between areas.

COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy Themes

COVID-19 TESTING IN SCHOOLS

Testing in schools is an important issue, with school closures having affected more than 55 million children in the United States. School closures affect children's development and their physical and mental health. The communities most impacted by the pandemic have experienced even more disparities. The latest research finds that:

- Children need to return to in-person school to regain access to important resources such as counseling, meals, social interaction, and after-school care.
- Transmission of COVID-19 in schools is generally low, and there is no correlation between in-school infections and community positivity rate. Safety measures such as testing, masking, and social distancing help to keep transmission low.
- Testing allows schools to determine if other strategies to prevent COVID-19 are working. It also allows schools to catch mild or asymptomatic cases of COVID-19 and prevent further spread.

STRENGTHENING MULTI-SECTOR PARTNERSHIPS

How can we build partnerships to bridge gaps in COVID-19 testing and vaccination capacities? The latest research finds that:

- Public-private partnerships are critical to pandemic preparedness and response, enabling the swift pace of COVID-19 vaccine production, distribution, and uptake.
- Community-engaged research ensures that communities are represented in the scientific process and is essential both for science and social accountability.
- Community-engaged research builds long-term, trusting relationships between researchers and community members.

COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy Themes

DATA SHARING EQUITY

How can data sharing across sectors improve community health in the COVID-19 pandemic and beyond? The latest research finds that:

- Data sharing can reveal health disparities, guide the sharing of resources, and improve quality of care and research.
- There is a need for data infrastructure that makes it easier for hospitals, health officials, decision makers, and the public to share complete and consistent data throughout the pandemic and in the future.
- There are many challenges to data sharing, but a few key improvements can advance data quality and ease COVID-19's impact.

ESTABLISHING COMMUNICATIONS FRAMEWORKS

How can we effectively communicate about COVID-19 to multiple audiences? The latest research finds that:

- The evolving nature of the pandemic poses challenges to clear, consistent, accurate communication between stakeholders.
- Community and culturally tailored messages that consider factors such as language, literacy level, and lived experience are essential for communicating with communities that are most impacted by the virus.
- Communicators need to be equipped to correct misinformation and distrust by providing clear and accurate information. 48% of people who live in the United States have been exposed to misinformation about COVID-19.
- Social distancing has moved communications online, but many people remain without access to the internet. Establishing efficient communication frameworks now can improve awareness of testing and vaccination benefits, address community questions and concerns, and strengthen communications in future crises.

Key Takeaways and Recommendations

COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy

EA2 Key Takeaways and Recommendations

- During Day 1 of EA2, two concurrent breakout sessions (2 per theme) yielded 12 separate presentations from 17 diverse speakers representing both community-based organizations (CBOs) and academic institutions. Brief summaries of the presenters' key takeaways by theme were shared back in the main conference. The key takeaways generated are listed on the following slides.
- On Day 2 of EA2, participants joined thematic round tables to generate group recommendations for improving infrastructure for equitable testing and vaccinations. Given the diversity of participants in EA2, the recommendations may be broadly applied by teams working in partnership with communities. Recommendations for action were summarized thematically and reported out to the main session. The recommendations generated are listed on the following slides.

Surge and Routine Testing: Key Takeaways

- Build coalitions made up of policymakers, scientists, and people with lived experience.
- Balance policy uniformity with context-dependent needs.
- Establish policies that address technology infrastructure and access disparities.
- Establish permanent solutions, not just pop-up solutions.
- Bring together projects with common approaches to help pool data and share strategies.

Surge and Routine Testing: Key Takeaways

- *Potential pathways for mass testing in low-density and rural areas – three strategies in rural Illinois:*
 - **Schools:** While schools are important gathering locations to reach the community, they are not and do not want to be healthcare providers. During the pandemic, schools successfully partnered with the state for additional resources. Trust, language, beliefs, and misinterpretation of data were important considerations.
 - **Wastewater:** Testing of wastewater allowed identification of global trends and is a tool that can be used for early detection to prepare healthcare systems by anticipating cases a week in advance.
 - **Mobile Clinics:** In rural areas, there are limited relationships with healthcare providers so community partnerships are key. Mobile clinics required special considerations: Healthcare deserts, migrant workers (travel, low working protection, language), and cultural/political diversity.

Surge and Routine Testing: Recommendations

- **Break the silos:** we focus on funding resources of single diseases at a time, but in practice, they are concurrent with many other health and social needs. Focus on addressing all social determinants of health and co-occurring diseases!
- **Not everyone has the same needs:** Be flexible regarding what services and resources can be provided. For example, leverage the COVID-19 testing effort to screen and test for other issues (e.g., chronic disease, HIV, and others)
- **Access:** Provide free tests to households; have consistent and persistent messaging around testing, including updates on current guidelines for testing; consistency in testing location and time.

Pandemic Preparedness: Key Takeaways

- ***LEAD Coalition of Bay County, Inc.:***

- The original goal of the program was to address gun violence.
- After hearing more from the community, LEAD revised its goal to create safe, resilient neighborhoods.
- LEAD partnered with Resilience American Communities to tackle issues related to COVID-19.
- Vaccine hesitancy was addressed via trusted messengers.

- ***Champaign-Urbana Public Health District:***

- Relationships were cultivated and maintained with community partners even when they were not actively experiencing a public health crisis.
- Equitable practices were employed in COVID-19 vaccination appointment-making.
- Participant recruitment was increased by offering additional services with vaccinations.

Pandemic Preparedness: Recommendations

- Maintain relationships with community partners even when they are not experiencing a public health crisis. Update points of contact regularly to ensure that connections are current.
- Establish relationships with philanthropic organizations.
- Educate folks on understanding public health from a very young age in order to effectively combat misinformation.
- Empower folks on where to receive accurate information on an ongoing basis.
- At a policy level, eliminate copays at federally qualified health centers.
- Principles of community engagement
 - Trust and transparency
 - Openness and learning

COVID-19 Testing in Schools: Key Takeaways

- *How **Los Angeles County** implemented a countywide COVID-19 testing program focused on marginalized communities:*
 - **Collaboration:** Worked with hundreds of partners including clinics, subject matter experts, and community organizations to establish a technical assistance framework.
 - **Communication:** Message early and often to all stakeholders. LA County established a weekly outreach strategy to share COVID information with partners in culturally and linguistically appropriate forms.
 - **Technology:** Mapping and dashboards were instrumental in identifying testing sites, hotspots, and testing deserts, as well as comparing testing demographics to county demographics to identify gaps and disparities where additional resources could be deployed.

COVID-19 Testing in Schools: Recommendations

- Historical and current trauma and mistreatment in healthcare inform behavior and response to public health disasters including the COVID-19 pandemic.
- Consider the importance of cultural values and how language informs how we frame testing and vaccines.
- Policy implications:
 - Examine how to get the most efficient use of resources to populations while weighing which form of government – whether that was federal or state – communities trusted the most and identify partners that share core values.
 - Ensure that adequate funding reaches all communities and translate related materials so they are widely accessible.
 - Invest in the care team.
 - Develop care delivery platforms that meet people where they are (which could be CBOs or other organizations that are trusted partners).

Strengthening Multi-Sector Partnerships: Key Takeaways

- Address entire well-being of community members (physical, mental, social and spiritual)
- Think broadly about sectors (housing, food, civic organizations, employers, public agencies, elected officials, faith-based organizations, social influencers)
- Break down internal and external silos
- Create safe spaces for dialogue and validate hesitancy
- Direct external resources towards community priorities versus pulling community resources to address outside priorities
- Develop relationships outside of crises
- Address immediate needs and build infrastructure at the same time
- Think of community members in terms of “Us” not “Them”

Strengthening Multi-Sector Partnerships: Recommendations

- Address gaps in technology access and literacy.
- Direct resources to where the communities need support in what their priorities are vs. coming in with an agenda.
- Make sure community partners are at the table driving the decisions that are being made (both on the research and clinical side of work).
- Build infrastructure and sustainability directly into communities rather than funneling it through larger institutions. Community organizations are always there; large institutions come and go.
- Ask before you direct funding to outsiders; direct funding within the community

Data Sharing Equity: Key Takeaways

- There is the systematic erasure of many groups in US data.
 - We are conducting research, publishing in peer-reviewed journals, and making public health decisions based on just a portion of the population.
 - We need disaggregated data by race/ethnicity and by subgroups to better understand specific health disparities within these groups.
 - We cannot default to putting groups into the “other”/ “missing” category under the guise of protecting those with small numbers. Strategies exist to collect and present data and still protect individuals.
 - When doing secondary data analysis using already existing data, we need to contextualize findings to better reflect the history of communities and their needs.
- Having community-specific data allows for tailored interventions and partnering with trusted community members and organizations can help us leverage data to tailor engagement strategies and deliver COVID19 education, prevention, health care, and vaccination efforts.
- We need to learn from each other, particularly from other communities of color, in finding our own communities’ voices and advocating for what we need. Better data can help with this.

Data Sharing Equity: Recommendations

- Do not rush the design phase of data collection; involve communities from the beginning when instruments for data collection are designed so that collected data is relevant and easy to obtain.
- Recognize the incredible diversity of communities. Adjust data collection instruments so they are relevant for specific projects.
- Be proactive about sharing across and within communities, particularly making sure that communities with access to fewer resources receive support and knowledge-sharing from more resource-rich communities.
- Create space and pathways for less-resourced communities.

Establishing Communication Frameworks: Key Takeaways

- Trusted voices are necessary, but not sufficient in messaging efforts.
- Effective messaging must incorporate cultural considerations and strong community partnerships.
- Messaging strategies must address stigma, discomfort, fears around documentation status, misinformation, and technological barriers.
- Misinformation is not a new concept; there is a broader historical context.
- We must take a holistic approach to study misinformation; simply tracking it does not sufficiently explain community dynamics or explore the context.
- Misinformation can offer hope and social connection, which we must keep in mind when framing accurate information.
- We need to focus more on building trust and less on blaming those who do not trust us by 1) encouraging compassion, 2) embracing translation opportunities, 3) learning what people are encountering, and 4) empowering information seeking.

Establishing Communication Frameworks: Recommendations

- *Cultural humility & respect*
 - Maintain cultural humility and respect for communities that you are serving, including being mindful of the space you are taking up.
 - Messaging & communication frameworks must be cognizant of how people self-identify and communicate through that lens - don't force people into categories.
 - Apply scalable, applicable, and effective technology to best support individual communities while ensuring that it is encompassing cultural humility and respect; develop tools that encompass cultural humility in promoting health literacy & integrate trust and understanding into service-learning curricula.
 - Be mindful about evaluating our impact in communities: ensure that our intentions are actually being met with regard to community representation and implementing change
 - Be respectful of cultural timelines, cadence, and rhythm. Include community partners at every step to be in sync with communities.

Establishing Communication Frameworks: Recommendations

- *Importance of community partners*
 - Champions from communities are critical for establishing connections and trust.
 - Work with partners to design materials from the very beginning
- *Address barriers to an authentic partnership*
 - Embrace true partnership with communities and address institutional policies and procedures that hinder this process.
 - Revise funding structures so community researchers receive equitable funding for their work.
 - Embrace transparency - create outreach materials (infographics) that explain and bring transparency to how we approach RADx-UP work

Case Examples from EA2 Presenters

How We Can Apply Takeaways to Our Work

Case Example 1: Lessons Learned and Strategies Taken by an Urban Indian Health Service

Virginia Hendrick, MPH, Executive Director of California Consortium for Urban Indian Health (CCUIH)

Hakeem O. Adeniyi, Jr., MD, Chief Medical Officer of Sacramento Native American Health Center, Inc.

Equity Evidence Academy 2 Breakout Session Presenters for "Vaccine and Testing Policies Big & Small"

- **Recognize and Address the Impact of Historical and Current Traumas and/or Mistreatment**

- **Lessons Learned:**

- Learn about the lived experiences of the communities that you wish to serve*

- Be mindful of one's assumptions of community member beliefs*

- Understand that one conversation is unlikely to undo years of trauma*

- Recognize the impact of governmental alliances on the community*

- Connect with trusted community partners for needs assessments*

Case Example 1: Lessons Learned and Strategies Taken by an Urban Indian Health Service

- **Address the Needs of Diverse Populations**

- Presenters called on participants to remember the importance of recognizing AI/AN populations are incredibly diverse.
- Examples of cultural and socioeconomic factors that should be considered when engaging AI/NA communities may be:

Access to education and income.

Eligibility and/or enrollment in Medicare or Medicaid

Status as an Indian Health Service Beneficiary

Enrollment in a tribal nation

- **Lessons Learned:**

Figure out who and what your priorities are

Invest in the Care Team (ensuring the safety of staff providing services through resources, such as PPE)

Determine your care delivery platform

Advocate while you work

Leverage your internal resources (as an example the speaker shared that SNAHC staffed COVID -19 testing sites with employees who were unable to perform regular duties due to the pandemic)

Case Example 1: Lessons Learned and Strategies Taken by an Urban Indian Health Service

- **Managing Local, County, and Federal Contracts to Address Community Needs**

- **Lessons Learned:**

Understand the deliverables prior to commitment (presenters emphasized that they needed to ensure organizations that they entered partnerships with had similar priorities in terms of what populations were being served as a function of the partnerships)

- Avoid over-committing
- Align organizational goals
- Prepare to pivot with changing needs
- Recognize the implications of affiliation agreements

Case Example 1: Lessons Learned and Strategies Taken by an Urban Indian Health Service

- **Leveraging Partnerships with CBOs to Achieve Equity**

- Presenters shared their experience in working with other CBOs to coordinate the delivery of services in a centralized location to make it easier for community members to get essential items they needed. Service providers had observed incredibly stressed families, particularly, multi-generational, trying to get their whole family tested and get other needed resources without missing work, which could be financially devastating. Long lines at overcrowded testing sites were not a good option for the community so they pivoted to a new model and provided a resource hub of testing, school supplies, food boxes, and services for emotional and mental health and domestic abuse.

- **Lessons Learned:**

- Confirm engagement from involved parties*

- Address evolving public health concerns*

- Prioritize contingency planning*

- Prepare to share the spotlight*

- Examine subcontracts and associated organization*

Case Example 2: Promoting Health Equity Through Evidence-Based Policy Development

Kenneth Fox, MD, *Chief Health Officer of Chicago Public Schools*

Equity Evidence Academy 2 Breakout Session Presenter for "Vaccine and Testing Policies Big & Small"

- **Lesson 1: Build on the Fundamentals**

- Establish your policy development team's credibility as experts by engaging your internal or external work groups that have a previously established reputation as trustworthy sources of information and resources. CPS OSHW were already positioned in the community as a credible organization for addressing students' health, which positioned them in the community as have the skills and expertise to develop a student health related policy.
- Build your policy on widely accepted existing credible evidence. CPS OHSW had already built their department on the existing evidence related to child health, which provided a solid foundation for selecting the policy's protocols.
- Anticipate that there may be those who do not agree with your policy being approved and prepare in advance for how you will address challenges as they arise.

Case Example 2: Promoting Health Equity Through Evidence-Based Policy Development

- **Lesson 2: Exercise Transparency**

- Make resources and evidence easily accessible to your target audience. By providing the evidence behind your policies and providing accurate information you can reduce the power of those who may be spreading misinformation.
- Build a communications channel that stays up to date in terms of current data, what resources you have available to your audience, and how they can gain access to those resources. CPS built data dashboards to communicate their data on indicators such as quarantine numbers, contact tracing, vaccine coverage, and testing. They also mapped COVID-19 testing and vaccines resources in the community.
- Market your key messages so that they are visible in the community. CPS conducted a mass marketing campaign across the city on billboards, bus shelters, and social media with messages encouraging parents to have their children vaccinated and highlighting their website as a source of information. If paid marketing is not an option for your organization, there are low-cost and no-cost ways to conduct marketing.

Case Example 2: Promoting Health Equity Through Evidence-Based Policy Development

- **Lesson 3: 'Politics is Medicine'**

- Be aware of the current political climate of the system you are working to effect so you can plan your policy advocacy strategies accordingly.
- Employ trusted allies who are in positions to influence the decision-makers who will ultimately approve your policy. can help you advocate for the approval of your policy. Organizational leadership, community leaders and local, state and federal lawmakers are just a few examples of allies to build relationships with.
- Fox noted that politics can be the medicine or the poison to creating equity. Recognize that social and political power can drive inequities. Investing time in building skills and learning about how to effectively engage in the political arena may go far to have policies pass that disrupt those that have systematically worked against health equity.
- Stay abreast of media coverage related to your policy and how it may influence public support. Be proactive in having your message highlighted favorably in media by employing best practices for media relations and leverage other communications channels your community uses to build support.

Case Example 3: Utilizing Data Mapping for COVID-19 Testing Resources Allocation

Clemens Hong, MD, *Acting Director of Community Programs, Los Angeles County Department of Public Health*

Equity Evidence Academy 2 Breakout Session Presenter for "COVID-19 Surge and Routine Testing"

- **Strategies for Leveraging Data to Affect Your Community's Health:**
 - If your team doesn't have trained data analysis professionals, take the time to consult one to make sure you truly understand what the data is telling you. This will save time and resources and lead to a more impactful outcome.
 - Create or tap into a mechanism that allows you to communicate with your communities early and often. Consider what data and/or relevant information your team has that will help inform the decision-making of individuals and your partners.

Case Example 3: Utilizing Data Mapping for COVID-19 Testing Resources Allocation

- **Strategies for Leveraging Data to Affect Your Community's Health Continued:**
 - If you are responding and planning your efforts based on real-time data, (as an example LAPHD was analyzing positive case numbers by geographic area to inform where to set up popup testing sites, which changed frequently) ensure a communications strategy to inform stakeholders in real-time. Your partners who are helping you spread information should be updated regularly as well as the public.
 - Strengthen partnerships by providing tools that make their work easier. As an example, the LAPHD used its capacity and expertise to provide communication messaging tools to its partners who were working directly with community members. This may open up partners' capacities to assist your organization with your needs.
 - Consider all the languages and literacy levels of your target populations and ensure messages are provided equitably to meet your community's diverse needs.
 - Follow the science and data and be flexible enough that you can switch course as the situation in your community evolves.

Case Example 4: Tailoring Messaging to Your Communities to Sustain Trust and Promote Health

Irene DeBarraicua, *Director of Operations, Lideres Campesinas*

Equity Evidence Academy 2 Breakout Session Presenters for "Building Communications Frameworks"

- **Strategies for Creating and Disseminating Impactful, Tailored COVID-19 Messages to Marginalized Communities:**
 - Recognize that using 'trusted voices' is a necessary foundation for sharing messages but not enough to capture the attention of communities who may be experiencing information overload from multiple media sources, which leads to inattention.
 - Make your messages stand out by avoiding 'canned' talking points. Instead, speak to how testing can directly benefit the individual and reduce their real-world problems. As an example, Lideres Campesinas demonstrated how testing is a step individuals can take to keep their families healthy and avoid illness.

Case Example 4: Tailoring Messaging to Your Communities to Sustain Trust and Promote Health

- **Strategies for Creating and Disseminating Impactful, Tailored COVID-19 Messages to Marginalized Communities Continued:**
 - Carefully select technical/research staff who are familiar with the specific communities you want to reach. It will likely ensure that messages are delivered with cultural sensitivity, patience, understanding, and in a language the community members will understand.
 - Prepare and train messengers to be prepared and able to listen deeply to community members to earn trust and make educational experiences engaging conversations rather than 'boring' lectures.
 - Use the forms of communication that the community relies on for information to disseminate messages. For example, Lideres Campesinas was aware that many migrant farmers have cell phones and use social media. Messages were posted not only on the organization's and community partners' social media pages but also staff members shared messages on their personal pages

Case Example 5: Planning Projects in Partnership with Community that Lead to Action

Caleb King, MSc, Health & Strategy Lead, Cook Inlet Tribal Council

Equity Evidence Academy 2 Breakout Session Presenter for *“Strengthening Multi-Sector Partnerships”*

- **Tips for Community-Engaged Participatory Project Planning:**

- Before developing goals for community projects, take the time to understand and engage with the existing goals of that community.
- Avoid paternalistic strategies, which attempt to impact communities through the following steps: ‘cold connecting’, diagnosing problems, prescribing solutions, and directing the community’s capacity.
- Understand that diagnosing a problem without community input can divert its resources, which may already be scarce, to outsiders’ intended goals instead of the goals of the community, which should always be prioritized.
- Conduct community forums regularly (Alaska Native corporations hold them annually) to determine and redetermine priorities and decide which organizations will take ownership of each one.
- Priority ownership should be redistributed based on community capacity. As an example, King said during the pandemic, hospitals’ responsibilities were redistributed to account for their reduced capacities

Case Example 5: Planning Projects in Partnership with Community that Lead to Action

- Key steps for following the community-based participatory project development model are:

- Building Relationships

- Engaging in inquiry

*Ask the community: What are your goals? Do you mind sharing your strategic plan with me? What do you all see as a priority in your community? **What gap can I fill v. this is the gap I want to fill?***

- Facilitating Community Ideation

Provide the infrastructure to the goal of the community versus asking the community to fill the infrastructure needed to fulfill your goal

Provide infrastructure to the already existing goals versus building infrastructure for your goals

- Always Respect Sovereignty

- Recognize that when partnering with understudied populations, particularly small and unique communities such as an individual tribal nation, there may not be an evidence-based approach or existing data to consult during the planning process.

- Consider incorporating a Plan-Do-Act-Study (PDSA) problem-solving model approach when planning projects. King's experience is that research projects that have been conducted in their community have often focused on the Study and Do steps but never actually reach the Act phase of implementation. To avoid this common misstep, he recommends the PDSA model of projection implementation so that evaluation is done in a continuous cycle while action is being taken and plans are continuously adapted for improvement.

Learn More: Access Full Presentations, Slides, Summary Report and More

Use the following links to access more information about the Evidence Academy and RADx-UP project resources:

- [COVID-19 Evidence Equity Academy Homepage](#)
 - [Evidence Academy 2- Looking Forward: Bridging Infrastructures for Equitable COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination](#)
 - [Evidence Academy 1- Translating Innovations in Testing](#)
- [RADx-UP Resources](#)
- [RADx-UP Project Publications](#)
- [RADx-UP Year in Review](#)

Thank you.

RADx-UP Evidence Academy events are held annually. Be sure to check the website for the next event!

For more information about our RADx-UP project, contact:

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